
Print to Digital: Transforming Intellectual Property Management in Libraries

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Abstract:

The times are changing. With Internet access and electronic reading devices, visiting the library is no longer a necessity for today's students. The library has changed a great deal over the past decade, due to changing demands from researchers, teachers, and learners and the onset of a digital revolution of library holdings. Digital transformation is powered by disruptive digital technologies, insights, and processes. The key focus of digital transformation is on transforming for the digital age by influencing customer experience, innovation, and efficiency. The big challenge with digital transformation is 'how fast and how far should organizations go on their digital transformation path'. Digital transformation journey is complicated and involves varied objectives, complexities, and covers a vast area. It requires a coherent and well-organized digital strategy to effectively address technology and process transformation together with supporting governance and delivery models.

Keywords: *Digital age, Academic Digital libraries, Transformation, Intellectual property, Digital transformation. etc.*

Introduction:

The information and communication technologies or the digital technologies enables the easy transmission, access and retrieval of various digital contents and materials available in libraries over the Internet, on-line through interactive networks. Providing access to books on shelves in library and to provide access to electronic resources/digital materials are totally different. While collecting, preserving and providing access to digital resources, it is a great concern to achieve an appropriate balance between copyright owners and users, which is also a topic of worldwide discussions from a legal perspective in academic and library fraternity. The very purpose of a digital library or digital archive is to collect, ensure long-term preservation or to provide an easy

and convenient means of access to its subject matter.

Digital Library and Digital Collection: Definitions:

Digitization is a process of converting the content of physical media (analog) in to digital format.

Digital Library:

An informal definition of a digital library is a “managed collection of information, with associated services, where the information is stored in digital formats and accessible over a network” (William Arms, Digital Libraries, 1999)

“A focused collection of digital objects, including text, video, and audio, along with methods for access and retrieval, and for selection, organization, and

maintenance of the collection”. (Witten and Bainbridge, How to Build a Digital Library 2003)

Digital Objects:

The digital library consists of objects like still images- photographs; textual documents-books, journals, thesis etc, ; moving images-video; audio; raw data files-statistical; complex objects- combination of more than one and others materials which are worth the use.

Digital Collection:

The digital collection consists of digital objects that are selected and organised to facilitate their access and use and good digital collections include metadata used to describe and manage them including copyright cleared (NISO: A Framework of guidance for building good collections 2007).

Types of Digital Collection:

There are mainly two types of documents covered in the digital library. One is born digital which means the documents is generated in digital form while it was created and there may or may not be parallel document in print form. The second one is converted from print to digital using all required technological tools and preserved for future use.

Components of Digital Library:

Following are the four essential elements for a digital library:

- Content- collection & metadata
- Technology- Enabling tools
- Users – user interface
- Services- digital library services in different form & varieties

Developing collection needs clearance of intellectual property rights specifically copyrights of the respective authors or owners of the rights.

Planning for a Digital Library:

Planning for digital library or developing digital collection involves following major steps:

- Defining set of goals and scope of the digital library collections
- Critical evaluation and selection of reading materials to be digitized
- Obtaining copyrights or permission to digitize the resource
- Determining technologies required with clear specifications (both hardware and software)
- Creating workflows so that redundancy can be avoided
- Preparing budget required to execute digitization work

What is Intellectual Property Rights:

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) is not a new concept. It is believed that IPR initially started in North Italy during the Renaissance era. In 1474, Venice issued a law regulating patents protection that granted an exclusive right for the owner. The copyright dates back to 1440 A.D. when Johannes Gutenberg invented the printing press with replaceable/moveable wooden or metal letters. Late in the 19th century, a number of countries felt the necessity of laying down laws regulating IPR.

Intellectual Property (IP) refers to creations of the mind: inventions; literary and artistic works; and symbols, names and images used in commerce.

Copyright:

Covers literary works (such as novels, poems and plays), films, music, artistic works (e.g., drawings, paintings, photographs and sculptures) and architectural design. Rights related to copyright include those of performing artists in their performances, producers of phonograms in their recordings, and broadcasters in their radio and television programs.

What is Copyright:

The Copyright is a right given by the law to creators of literary, dramatic, musical and artistic works and producers of cinematograph films and sound recordings.

In fact, it is a bundle of rights including, inter alia, rights of reproduction, communication to the public, adaptation and translation of the work.

Copyright includes:

The reproduction right (the right to make copies):

For purposes of the reproduction right, a “copy” of a work is any form in which the work is fixed and from which it can be perceived, reproduced, or communicated, either directly or with the aid of a machine.

- ❖ **The right to create adaptations, or derivative works:** A “derivative work” is a work that is based on a copyrighted work, but contains new material that is original in the copyright sense. For example, Windows 2000 is a derivative work based on Windows 98.
- ❖ **The right to distribute copies of the work to the public:** The distribution right is limited by the “first sale doctrine,” which provides that the owner of a particular copy of a copyrighted work may sell or transfer that copy. In other words, the copyright owner, after the first sale of a copy, cannot control the subsequent disposition of that copy.
- ❖ **The right to perform the work publicly:** To “perform” a work means to recite, render, play, dance, or act it, with or without the aid of a machine. For e.g. a live concert is a performance of a musical composition, as is the playing of a CD on which the composition is recorded.
- ❖ **Managing Copyright Issues in Digital Library:** It is important for the professionals to understand and adhere to copyright issues involved in developing digital collection (s) as part of their digital library. Any document which is added as part of digital library and access is provided for wider use on the Internet has to

have copyright cleared or one has to ensure that it does not violate copyrights of the author or the owner of the rights. Following are some the ways how one could manage copyright related issues:

- ❖ **Documents in public domain:** Some of the often used documents which are considered for addition in the digital library and if they happen to be available in the public domain as a policy for wider use, one can safely add these to the collection.
- ❖ **Written agreements & permissions:** Documents considered for digitisation but copyright rests with authors or publisher, one will have seek the written agreement with certain clear terms and condition. Then only such documents could be added to the collection.
- ❖ **Licensed resources:** There are certain documents where copyright holders have clearly stated what can be done with such documents and what cannot be done. Depending on the stated policy or licenses, one can consider adding documents to digital library.
- ❖ **Creative Commons:** Presently, number of documents are generated in electronic only format. These are generated by individuals, institutions, associations, funding agencies, government departments and others. Considering either as policy mandate or other factors which favour authors and users, these documents are made available under any one of the six Creative Commons licenses. Depending on these licenses, one may decide to include documents in the digital collection. The major issues are:
 - Is digitization to be considered as similar to reproduction, for example using Xerox machine?

- Is digitization a deductive activity such as translation from one language to another?
- Can transmission of digitized documents through Internet be considered as commercial distribution or public communication similar to broadcasting?
- Is the principle of exhaustion of the distribution right still effective in the digital age?
- In the digital context if access could be technologically restricted by the copyright owner, how could the public exercise fair use with regard to those work?

The copyright protects creative works. Simply transformation in to the digital form of an original document cannot be considered as creative. Further, there is an increasing shift away from the model of the library as a physical repository/archive of information are facts to provision of licensed access to digital resources. Libraries are dealing with many e-books, e-journals publishers and vendors (the rights holders); negotiating and signing contracts agreements to get access to e-resources by paying subscription fees for a specified limited time. Copyrights are moreover now being replaced by contracts agreements in between libraries and publishers. There, libraries could ask rights holders for permission to copy those subscribed e-resources for preservation purposes or for perpetual access to those resources.

Conclusion:

Digital libraries serve as an important source for preservation and widening the access to documents which are rare, important and which are otherwise not easily accessible. Digital Library consists set of collection(s) of documents which either born digital or converted from print to digital. Since most these documents are covered by Copyrights (rights owned by authors or

publisher) it become imperative for the professional involved in creating digital libraries to ensure that these rights not violated. Since there are number of provisions as to how one could manage the copyright, it is important to understand these provisions and manage them effectively. This module presented some of those ways how one could manage the copyright related issues.

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